

PHOSPHORUS SOURCES AND TRANSPORT IN AN AGRICULTURAL RIVER BASIN OF LAKE ERIE

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Abstract. The mean annual export of total phosphorus (as P) from a 3237 km² (1251 mi²) portion of the Sandusky River Basin was determined to be 454 metric tons (500 short tons). Annual point source inputs of phosphorus within the study area were observed to be 118 metric tons (130 short tons). Assuming all point source phosphorus leaves the system, a minimum diffuse source component of the output would be 336 metric tons (370 short tons) or 74% of the total output. This represents a diffuse phosphorus loading coefficient of 103 kg/yr/km² (591 lb/yr/mi²), a value 2.4 times as large as the 44 kg/yr/km² (250 lb/yr/mi²) which is used to calculate rural runoff in much of the Lake Erie Basin. During 1972, a year of high runoff, in excess of 980 metric tons (1078 short tons) of phosphorus moved out of the study area.

It is suggested that the diffuse source loading coefficient represents a eutrophication index related to land use in the study area. The reduction of phosphorus loading into Lake Erie from diffuse sources will require comprehensive land use planning and implementation. Reduced values for the diffuse phosphorus loading coefficient, corrected for annual variations in runoff, would provide a measure of progress towards less eutrophic land use management in the basin. (Key words: point source; diffuse source; annual export; total phosphorus; eutrophication index; Lake Erie).

INTRODUCTION

The sources of the phosphorus which enter streams and lakes may be described as either point sources or diffuse sources. An example of a point source of phosphorus is provided by the phosphorus which enters streams or lakes as part of the effluent of municipal sewage treatment plants. Although this phosphorus is, for a while, distributed throughout a whole city, town or sewage district, sewage collection systems carry this phosphorus to central treatment plants where, if not removed, the phosphorus enters the receiving stream through a pipe, i.e., a point source. Other point sources of phosphorus include combined sewer overflows, storm sewers and industrial effluent outfalls. In general, point sources consist of relatively small volumes of flow containing relatively high concentrations of phosphorus.

Diffuse sources of phosphorus consist of numerous, low intensity, widely distributed sources. A major component of the phosphorus of diffuse origin is a consequence of erosion, since the soil particles that become part of the sediment load of streams retain much of the phosphorus that was originally bound to them. The selective erosion of the finer soil particles can even result in higher phosphorus contents within the sediment than in the parent soil. Burrows and Kilmer (1963) have shown an enrichment ratio (ratio of amount of element in sediment to original soil) of 3.4 for phosphorus. Thus all land areas susceptible to erosion, such as cultivated fields, stream banks and construction sites, represent potential diffuse sources of phosphorus.

In addition to sediment-bound phosphorus, surface runoff water will also contain dissolved phosphorus. Drainage tile effluents, rural septic tanks, feed lots and even groundwater can also be considered diffuse sources of phosphorus. In contrast with point sources, diffuse sources of phosphorus generally yield large volumes of flow containing relatively low concentrations of phosphorus.

In this paper, the contribution of phosphorus from point sources and diffuse sources to the Sandusky River are examined. For diffuse phosphorus, the

annual yield per square kilometer is calculated. In addition, the phosphorus transport characteristics of the river system which determine the pattern of delivery of phosphorus from the river into Sandusky Bay and Lake Erie are noted. Evidence for short-term storage of point source phosphorus within the stream bed is also discussed.

Unfortunately, very little information is available on phosphorus transport in the river systems of the Lake Erie Basin. The only systematic study of phosphorus transport into Lake Erie was a limited one-year study published in 1968 by the Federal Water Pollution Control Administration (now Environmental Protection Agency) under the title, *Lake Erie South Shore Tributary Loading Data Summary, 1967* (U.S. Department of the Interior 1968a). The breakdown of phosphorus sources and loading which appears in the *Lake Erie Report* (U.S. Department of the Interior 1968b) and from which Table 6 is adapted, was generated in part by the use of factors such as 44 kg/yr/km² (250 lb/yr/mi²) for rural runoff and 93 kg/yr/km² (530 lb/yr/mi²) for urban

TABLE 1. Examples of stream flows, phosphorus concentrations, momentary phosphorus loadings and daily loadings at the Fremont stream gage of the Sandusky River. These measurements were taken during "runoff" events in the spring of 1972.

Date	Time of Collection	Flow (m ³ /sec)	Total phosphorus concentration (mg/l)	Momentary loading (kg/hr)	Phosphorus loading per 12- or 24-hr period (metric tons)
29 February	0830	10.8	.27	10.5	.252
2 March	1115	66.5	.48	114.9	1.379
2 March	1700	151	.58	315.3	3.780
3 March	0710	247	1.05	993.6	11.916
3 March	1615	211	.82	622.8	7.464
4 March	0940	177	.75	477.9	5.735
4 March	1630	162	.65	376.1	4.513
5 March	0850	126	.45	204.0	2.448
5 March	1630	112	.35	141.1	1.693
6 March	0800	75.8	.30	81.8	1.963
11 March	1535	17.2	.15	9.3	.223
14 March	0920	271	.62	604.9	7.248
14 March	1730	282	.68	690.3	8.280
15 March	0930	263	.62	587.0	7.044
15 March	1715	240	.58	501.1	6.013
16 March	0930	226	.53	431.2	5.172
16 March	1800	200	.37	226.4	2.717
17 March	0740	185	.28	186.5	2.238
17 March	1630	170	.29	177.5	2.130
18 March	0900	150	.27	145.8	3.499
19 March	0930	94.8	.23	78.5	1.884
20 March	0830	64.3	.23	53.2	1.277
18 April	0630	156	.71	398.7	4.784
18 April	1850	147	.68	359.8	4.318
19 April	0640	132	.56	266.1	3.193
19 April	2000	110	.56	221.8	2.662
20 April	1925	177	.44	280.3	6.727
21 April	1930	243	.95	831.1	19.946
22 April	1945	421	1.00	1515	36.360
23 April	1315	486	.76	1330	31.920

runoff. These factors should not be viewed as average values for the Lake Erie Basin based on extensive inbasin studies. Rather they were available factors which could be used for first approximations of phosphorus sources.

The Sandusky River Watershed

The Sandusky River is one of the north central Ohio tributaries to Lake Erie (Fig. 1). The river is about 185 km (115 mi) long and drains an area of 3680 km² (1421 sq mi), most of which is agricultural land. The profile of the river is extremely variable, ranging from a drop of less than 0.38 m/km (2 ft/mi) in many areas to other places, such as below Tiffin, where the fall is 4.7 m/km (25 ft/mi). The study area consists of the 3237 km² (1251 mi²) section of the river upstream from the U.S. Geological Survey stream gage near Fremont, Ohio which is indicated by the arrow in Fig. 1.

The southern 65% of the basin is in the Till Plain, which is traversed by a low east-west moraine south of Upper Sandusky and another south of Tiffin. The northern 35% of the basin is in the Lake Plains subprovince. The bedrock at or near the surface consists of dolomite, limestone and shale of Silurian and Devonian age. These formations are relatively dense and groundwater storage is not great. The overburden of glacial drift and lacustrine deposits are generally thin and relatively impermeable. In the southern part of the basin near Upper Sandusky, Bucyrus and Crestline, the drift thickens and is more permeable in the areas of morainal deposits.

The soils of the Sandusky Basin are variable. In the lake plain area, the very poorly drained Hoytville silty clay loam and clay are dominant. In the till plains, the soils are derived from moderately fine textured Wisconsin glacial till. In the western part of the till plain, the soils have developed over limestone, while in the eastern part they have developed over a sandstone-shale area. Throughout the basin, groundwater contribution to stream flow is small and sustained flow is low.

Land use inventories developed by the Soil Conservation Service in 1967 indicate that approximately 69% of the land area in the basin is used for cultivated crops, 9% for pasture land, 10% as woods, 6% for other rural uses and 6% for urban and other non-agricultural uses. The population of the entire basin is about 192,000.

River Transport Model

Figure 2 is a model of the approach to analyzing phosphorus inputs, storage and output used in this study. Phosphorus inputs are categorized as

FIG. 2. A model of material input, storage and output for a river system.

originating from either diffuse or point sources, as previously described. Movement of phosphorus from the flowing water to the stream bed can result in either short-term or long-term storage. If the phosphorus is readily resuspended during washout events or redissolved as a consequence of biological or physico-chemical processes, then its storage would be considered short term. The phosphorus which is trapped in sediments that either accumulate upstream from dams or are deposited on flood plains would be an example of long-term storage. The outputs of the system consist of the flowing water discharge at the downstream point of the drainage area and the bed load transport.

Of the above inputs, exchanges and outputs, direct measurements are most readily obtained on the flowing water output and the point source inputs. From these measurements, conclusions can be drawn with respect to minimum diffuse source components of the outputs. Also by comparing the temporal distribution of both point source inputs and the flowing water point output, some conclusions with respect to short-term storage of phosphorus can be obtained.

METHODS

The phosphorus measurements presented in this paper all represent total phosphorus as P. All phosphorus tests were done according to *Methods for Chemical Analysis of Water and Wastes* (Environmental Protection Agency 1971), using the single reagent, potassium antimony tartrate method. Optical densities were read with a Klett-Summerson colorimeter outfitted with a filter having a transmission maximum of 690 millimicrons. For total phosphate a persulfate acid hydrolysis was carried out. Samples were heated for 30 min in an autoclave at 15 pounds pressure. During times of high sediment concentration, the samples were filtered through a washed 0.45 μ membrane filter immediately after removal from the autoclave. All samples were then cooled, neutralized and tested as above. Suspended solids were also measured according to procedures described in *Methods for Chemical Analysis of Water and Wastes* (Environmental Protection Agency 1971).

Grab samples were collected from the bridge at the Fremont stream gage. At this location, the river flow is quite turbulent even at low flows. The stream bed consists of dolomitic bed rock. It is assumed that the finer sediment particles, which provide the bulk of the biding sites for phosphorus, are uniformly distributed in the flowing water. Replicate sampling at the bridge gave very close agreement.

RESULTS

Measurements of the Phosphorus Output via Flowing Water

The ideal way to measure phosphorus output of a river system would be to continuously monitor the phosphorus concentration at the discharge site. These data, along with corresponding continuous measurements of river flow, could be used to calculate the total amount of phosphorus moving out of the system. Although continuous measurements of stream flow are often available at stream gaging stations, data on phosphorus concentrations are generally far from continuous. During several periods of high runoff in the spring of 1972, water samples were collected daily or twice daily at the Fremont stream gage and analyzed for total phosphorus. The results of some of these analyses are shown in Table 1.

The data indicate that the phosphorus concentrations increase as the flow increases and that the phosphorus concentration changes very rapidly during the time interval surrounding the "crest" (see for example, 2 March at 1700; 3 March at 0710 and 3 March at 1615). Since the loading rate is the product of concentration and flow, the loading rate is changing most rapidly at the times when its values are highest. This makes accurate total phosphorus loading data very difficult to obtain. Increasing phosphorus concentrations with increasing stream flow in the Sandusky River have previously been noted by Baker and Kramer (1971).

The problems of obtaining accurate phosphorus loading measurements in river systems are quite similar to those involved in obtaining accurate sediment transport measurements. The latter topic is discussed thoroughly in papers by Guy (1970) and Guy and Norman (1970). The rapidly fluctuating concentrations of phosphorus during a single runoff event in the Sandusky River contrast markedly with the observations by Freve (1971). He reports that for the small agricultural watersheds at the North Appalachian Experimental Watershed at Coshocton, Ohio, the nutrient concentrations do not vary significantly during a single runoff event. The vastly different sizes of the watersheds (3237 km² for the Sandusky River Basin versus 3.1 ha for the largest agricultural watersheds at Coshocton) together with the different soil types and different topography make comparisons between Coshocton studies and studies of river systems in northwestern Ohio very difficult.

Since year-round intensive surveillance is not yet available, estimates of the total annual output of phosphorus must be based on an extrapolation of existing data. Two methods of extrapolation have been used in this study. The first method is the same as that used in the *Lake Erie South Shore Tributary Loading Data Summary* (U.S. Department of the Interior 1968a). It involves the use of a weighted mean loading rate per unit discharge. The weighted mean is calculated by dividing the sum of the momentary loadings by the sum of the corresponding momentary flows. Multiplying this value by the mean daily discharge during a given year and the days per year gives an annual loading figure. Using 166 individual measurements of phosphorus loading, which included measurements during all seasons of the year, the weighted mean phosphorus loading for the Sandusky River at Fremont was calculated to be 47 kg/day/m³/sec (2.92 lb/day/cfs).

The weighted mean phosphorus loading rate for the Sandusky River, as calculated from data in the *Lake Erie South Shore Tributary Loading Data Summary* (U.S. Department of the Interior 1968a) was 55 kg/day/m³/sec (3.45 lb/day/cfs). This value was based on 22 measurements of momentary loading from February 1967 to January 1968. The higher value is attributable to a single measurement on 29 January 1968 which had a high flow, 250 m³/sec

(8836 cfs), and an exceptionally high phosphorus concentration (1.14 mg/1 P). This single high value accounted for 56% of the total momentary loading observed during the study period. The Tributary Loading Data Summary does include the warning that the "limited frequency of sample collection, particularly during periods of high flow, could bias the data."

A second method for calculating annual phosphorus output involves the use of a graph relating loading rate to river flow. Figures 3 and 4 show these graphs for the output station. Figure 4 is an expanded scale graph of the low flow portion of Fig. 3. In Fig. 3, each point represents a single measurement of instantaneous loading. Considerable scatter of points is present, reflecting varying phosphorus concentrations at given flow rates. The data were reduced by calculating weighted mean loading rates, as described

FIG. 3. The relationship between daily phosphorus loading and streamflow. The derivation of curves is explained in the text.

FIG. 4. The relationship between daily phosphorus loading and streamflow for the low range streamflows.

previously, for individual flow intervals. For example, all the data between 6000 and 7000 cfs were used to calculate a weighted mean loading rate per unit discharge appropriate for that range of stream flows. The resulting loading rate per unit discharge was multiplied by the mid-range flow value (6500 cfs), giving an average loading rate at the mid-range flow. These values are plotted as the open circles on the graph from which the loading rate-stream discharge curve was drawn. Metric system units were subsequently added to the graph.

The solid line on the graph represents the slope of the weighted mean value when all the data points are used. For these data, it is the value (47 kg/day/m³/sec) that was cited above. Note that at both high and low stream flow values, the loading rate-stream flow curve differs significantly from the solid line.

To calculate annual loading of phosphorus using the graphs in Figs. 3 and 4, mean daily flows at the stations are individually evaluated for phosphorus loading and subsequently summed to give the annual figure. This method has two advantages. First, it gives a more realistic picture of the actual amount of phosphorus moving out of the system on a given day. Secondly, and more importantly, the annual output of phosphorus is more likely a function of the pattern of runoff events than the mean daily flow for the entire year. In other words, years with equal total annual water discharges could have different phosphorus (and sediment) loadings into Lake Erie, depending on the pattern of runoff events.

Estimates of the annual output of phosphorus from the study area for the 1970 water year, the 1972 calendar year and the mean year are shown in Table 2. Flow data used in the loading calculations were obtained from *Water Resource Data for Ohio, 1970* (U.S. Department of the Interior 1971) and from interim flow data supplied by the U.S. Geological Survey.¹ The calculations of phosphorus output based on weighted means and on the graphical summation gave essentially similar results. The figure based on the mean annual flow is quite similar to that estimated in the Environmental Protection Agency (U.S. Department of the Interior 1968a) study. Given the variations in the methods, a figure of 453 metric tons (500 short tons) per year seems reasonable for the mean annual output of phosphorus. The 1972 loading figures, which are twice as high as the mean figure, probably reflect the dominant role of diffuse sources in the loading of phosphorus from this basin into Lake Erie.

TABLE 2. Estimates of the annual output of total phosphorus from the Sandusky Basin at the Fremont stream gage.

Source and method	Metric tons of total phosphorus per year (short tons in parentheses)		
	1970 Water Year	1972 Calendar Year	Mean Annual Output
Heidelberg; weighted mean	441 (486)	980 (1080)	445 (490)
Heidelberg; graphical summation	464 (511)	1010 (1110)	— —
Lake Erie South Shore Tributary loading Data, 1967 weighted mean	— —	— —	484 (533)

¹U. S. Department of the Interior, Geological Survey, Washington, D. C.

TABLE 3. Estimates of annual point source loading of phosphorus into the Sandusky River upstream from the Fremont stream gage.

Town	Population	Combined Sewers (kg P per year)	Sewage Treatment Plant (kg P per year)	Total Point Source Loading (kg P per year)
Bucyrus	13,111	4160 ¹	22,200	26,400
Tiffin	21,596	7440	39,700 ²	47,100
Subtotal	34,707			73,500 (162,000 lbs)
Crestline	5947			
New Washington	1251			
Carey	3523			
Nevada	917	Population equivalent = 2.1 kg/year/person (4.7 lb/year/person)		
Sycamore	1096			
Upper Sandusky	5645			
Attica	1005			
Bettsville	833			
Bloomville	884			
Total	55,808			119,000 (262,000 lb)

¹Burgess and Niple Limited, 1969 (Stream pollution and abatement from combined sewer overflows).

²Data from Tiffin Sewage Treatment Plant.

Measurements of Phosphorus Inputs from Point Sources

Table 3 shows the data from which an estimate of total point source inputs of phosphorus was obtained. The estimate is based on direct measurements of phosphorus inputs from the two largest cities in the study area coupled with an extrapolation to the remainder of the cities and towns based on population.

The city of Bucyrus was the site of a study entitled *Stream Pollution and Abatement from Combined Sewer Overflows, Bucyrus, Ohio* (Burgess and Niple Limited 1969). The annual inputs of phosphorus from both combined sewers and the Bucyrus sewage treatment plant were obtained from that study. The phosphorus loading into the Sandusky River from the Tiffin Sewage Treatment Plant was obtained from the treatment plant records. The treatment plant proportionally composites samples of the plant effluent at two-hour intervals. Their analytical results gave essentially the same results as those of the authors.

Since no direct measurements of phosphorus loading from combined sewer overflows in Tiffin have been made, the value for combined sewer overflows in Tiffin was assumed to be the same proportion of the sewage treatment effluent as found in Bucyrus.

The total phosphorus loading from the two towns was divided by their populations, giving an in-basin population equivalent of 2.1 kg/yr/person (4.7 lb/yr/person). This value undoubtedly includes at least part of the "urban runoff" component of phosphorus loading. The value was multiplied by the total populations of the towns in the basin which either have existing sewage treatment facilities or may soon be required to construct sewage treatment facilities. The resulting figure constitutes an estimate of the annual phosphorus input from point sources. Further calculations will be based on a rounded-off figure of 118 metric tons/year (130 short tons/year). Since the

inputs of phosphorus loading from point sources are relatively constant (excluding diurnal fluctuations), the mean hourly input from all point sources in the basin would be 13.6 kg/hr (30 lb/hr).

Calculations of Diffuse Source Inputs

From the transport model (Fig. 2) it is apparent that if the mean annual phosphorus output is known and the annual point source inputs are known, a "minimum diffuse source component" of the flowing water output may be calculated. This calculation assumes that none of the point source inputs moves into long-term storage in the river system. Consequently average annual outputs of phosphorus originating from point source inputs should equal the annual point source inputs.

Subtracting the annual point source inputs of 118 metric tons/year (130 short tons/year) from the mean annual output of 454 metric tons (500 short tons) gives a minimum value of 336 metric tons (370 short tons) for the component of the annual output originating from diffuse sources. If 10% of the point source inputs were trapped in long-term sinks, then the diffuse source component of the output would increase to 345 metric tons (383 short tons).

Dividing the minimum annual diffuse source output of phosphorus (336 metric tons) by the total land area in the basin gives a diffuse phosphorus loading coefficient of 103 kg/yr/km². This value is approximately an order of magnitude higher than the phosphorus inputs per unit land area determined for the rivers which empty into the Bay of Quinte (Johnson and Owen 1971). The above value of the diffuse loading coefficient for the Sandusky Basin is also higher than any of those listed in the above paper.

Table 4 compares the diffuse source loading of phosphorus from this study area toward Lake Erie with the "rural runoff" estimate in the *Lake Erie Report* (U.S. Department of the Interior 1968b). Such comparisons must be indirect since the figures in the *Lake Erie Report* are for the entire North Central Ohio subbasin of Lake Erie. It appears, however, that the calculations of rural runoff in this subbasin were based on 44 kg/yr/km² (250 lb/yr/mi²). This would mean that in the study area the rural runoff should have been only 142 metric tons. If the diffuse loading coefficient can be extrapolated from 3237 km² to the entire North Central Ohio subbasin of Lake Erie, then total annual diffuse loading for the subbasin would be 1193 metric tons (1315 short tons). This is roughly 2.7 times the "rural runoff" estimate for this subbasin as listed in the *Lake Erie Report* (U.S. Department of the Interior 1968b).

TABLE 4. Comparisons of "diffuse source" phosphorus loading and "rural runoff" loading for both the Sandusky River Basin and the North Central Ohio Subbasin.

Area	Metric tons of Total Phosphorus (short tons in parentheses)	
	Heidelberg Study "Diffuse Source" Loading ¹	Lake Erie Report "Rural Runoff" Loading ²
Sandusky Basin (3237 km ²)	336 (370)	142 (156)
North Central Ohio Subbasin of Lake Erie (11,525 km ²)	1193 (1315)	430 (474)

¹The extrapolation to the North Central Ohio Subbasin is based on a diffuse source loading coefficient of 103 kg/yr/km².

²The Sandusky Basin "rural runoff" value is based on 44 kg/yr/km².

If other areas of northwestern Ohio have similar diffuse phosphorus loading coefficients, then diffuse phosphorus loading into Lake Erie is much larger than heretofore expected. It should be noted that both land use patterns and soil types in the much larger Maumee Basin are similar to those in the Sandusky River Basin.

Short-Term Storage of Phosphorus from Point Sources

One aspect of phosphorus transport in rivers, such as the Sandusky River, is the tremendous variation in the rate of phosphorus output. Table 5 provides examples of extremes in phosphorus output observed at the Fremont stream gage. Output rates varied from 1.92 kg/hr (4 lb/hr) to 1512 kg/hr (3350 lb/hr). Figure 5 shows the monthly distribution of phosphorus output from the study area for the 1970 water year.

Much of the time the rate of phosphorus output is less than the combined rates of point source inputs (13.6 kg/hr). Whenever the output of a river system is less than the rate of point source inputs into the river from all of the towns, it is apparent that phosphorus from point sources is moving into the storage compartment of the river system. In calculating the annual output of phosphorus for the 1970 water year using the graphical techniques, it was noted that 70% of the time the output rate was less than the total input rate from point sources. Since some components of the diffuse inputs must also continually be entering the river, a large part of the point source inputs must be moving into the storage compartment of the system.

It is not known what fraction of the point source phosphorus inputs moves into short-term stream bed storage and what fraction moves into long-term sinks. It is possible that most of the phosphorus from point sources that moves into the storage compartment is restricted to short-term sinks. Annual washout of this phosphorus could equal annual movement of phosphorus into the storage compartment, giving rise to a kind of annual steady-state transport. This assumption would mean that for the river system, the component of the annual outflow originating from point sources is equal to the annual point source inputs. This assumption was used previously in the calculation of the minimum diffuse source component of the output.

A second possibility would be that a large portion of the point source inputs becomes trapped in long-term sinks within the river system. Phosphorus bound to sediments which accumulates behind dams or which is deposited on flood plains could be entering long-term sinks and consequently not be subject to washout processes. If this is the case, phosphorus removal at domestic treatment plants will result in smaller than predicted reductions in the phosphorus output of the system. Furthermore, it would mean that the diffuse source contributions of phosphorus from this basin are even larger than the amounts shown in Table 4.

That phosphorus can move from flowing water to the stream bed is well documented (Keup 1968). To what extent such movement is mediated by biological, as opposed to purely physical-chemical mechanisms, is less sure. As pointed out by Taylor and Kunishi (1971), sediment itself can act as a scavenger and remove soluble phosphorus from flowing water. The effect of such scavenging on the phosphorus output of the river system depends on whether the sediments themselves are washed out of the system. In any event, most of the phosphorus originating from point sources that actually moves out of the system will do so during a "washout" event. At this time, the suspended solids concentrations will also be very high. Figure 6 shows the correlation between the concentrations of suspended solids and total phosphorus which were observed during March and April 1972.

TABLE 5. Extremes in momentary loading of total phosphorus at the Fremont stream gage, Sandusky River.

	Date	Flow (m ³ /sec)	Concentration (total P mg/l)	Momentary Loading (kg/hr)
Highs	22 April 1972	420	1.00	1512
	23 April 1972	485	.76	1327
	3 March 1972	246	1.05	929
	14 March 1972	281	.68	677
	29 January 1968	249	1.14	1021
Lows	11 August 1969	2.11	.32	2.43
	15 August 1969	2.00	.38	2.70
	4 September 1969	1.47	.43	2.30
	29 October 1969	1.72	.31	1.92
	Sandusky River point source loading rate			13.60 kg/hr 30 lb/hr

(Environmental Protection Administration datum)

TABLE 6. Sources of phosphorus within subbasins of Lake Erie expressed as percent of the total loading for each subbasin (U.S. Department of the Interior 1968a).

Subbasin	Point Sources			Urban Runoff	Point Source Subtotal	Diffuse Sources Rural Runoff	Percent of Total Lake Erie Loading for Subbasin
	Municipal Wastes	Industrial Wastes					
Southeast Michigan	84%	5%		5%	94%	6%	40%
Maumee River Basin	43%	5%		5%	53%	47%	15%
North Central Ohio	45%	6%		19%	70%	30%	6%
Greater Cleveland-Akron	86%	3%		8%	97%	3%	19%
Ontario	66%			3%	69%	31%	13%
(others)	58%	7%		13%	68%	22%	7%
Lake Erie Basin	72%	4%		7%	83%	17%	100%

FIG. 5. Monthly distribution of phosphorus output from the study area for the 1971 water year.

FIG. 6. The relationship between concentrations of suspended sediment and total phosphorus.

DISCUSSION

The data and analyses presented above paint a picture of phosphorus sources which is rather different from the usual tabulation for Lake Erie. In the *Lake Erie Report* published by the Federal Water Pollution Control Administration (U.S. Department of the Interior 1968b), phosphorus sources are divided into four categories: municipal waste, industrial waste, urban runoff and rural runoff. Of these, the first three are predominantly point sources, while the last is a diffuse source. Estimates of the relative contribution of each of these sources for the entire Lake Erie Basin and for individual sub-basins are shown in Table 6 which is adapted from the *Lake Erie Report* (U.S. Department of the Interior 1968b). These figures indicate that for the Lake Erie Basin as a whole, point source contributions are 83% of the annual phosphorus loading, while diffuse sources contribute 17%. Here, diffuse sources contribute at least 74% of the phosphorus moving out of the study area, while point sources contribute no more than 26%. In part, these percentages may reflect a rural bias in the study area. Yet population densities and land use are probably not substantially different here from those in a large part of the Lake Erie Basin.

There is a wide variation among the Lake Erie subbasins in the relative amounts of phosphorus originating from point and diffuse sources. Table 6 shows that diffuse sources range from 3% of the annual loading in the Cleveland-Akron area to 47% in the Maumee River Basin. Furthermore, for all of the subbasins, major metropolitan areas (point sources) are located along the shores of Lake Erie. As soon as one moves a relatively short distance inland from the Lake, it is apparent that the relative significance of point sources will decrease and diffuse sources will increase.

It is possible that the amount of phosphorus loading from diffuse sources into Lake Erie has been underestimated. The diffuse loading coefficient used in this study is 2.4 times as large as the 44 kg/yr/km² that was used to estimate rural runoff in the *Lake Erie Report* (U.S. Department of the Interior 1968b). If diffuse loading coefficients similar to those of the Sandusky River

hold for most of northwestern Ohio, considerably more phosphorus loading into Lake Erie will persist after the implementation of phosphorus removal at domestic sewage treatment plants than is currently predicted. Substantial reductions of phosphorus loading from diffuse sources may be necessary if desired reductions in phosphorus loading into Lake Erie are to be achieved.

At the present time, many of the cities within the study area are being required to install phosphorus removal equipment. It is probable that the benefits for Lake Erie from phosphorus removal by "inland" towns will be much less than the benefits of phosphorus removal from towns of comparable size located along the Lake Erie shores. Some of the phosphorus originating from inland towns may never reach Lake Erie. Most of such phosphorus that does reach Lake Erie will arrive during the times of the year when high sediment and diffuse source phosphorus loading is simultaneously occurring. The component of the total output from the river that originates from point sources may arrive in forms in which, and at times when, its biological impact will be much less than point source loading by cities located near the lake. It is uncertain to what extent the "biological activity" of the phosphorus originating from point sources, that "first" accumulates on the stream bed and "then" washes out of the system, differs from the "biological activity" of phosphorus adsorbed onto inorganic sediments. The answer to this question may be important in evaluating the biological impact within Lake Erie of phosphorus removal at "inland" domestic sewage treatment plants.

Also the biological significance of sediment bound phosphorus originating from diffuse sources depends largely on its release from the sediments after they are deposited in the lake bed.

Johnson and Owen (1971) have pointed out that point sources of phosphorus which empty directly into the Bay of Quinte, Lake Ontario have a much greater impact on the concentration of phosphorus in the bay than the phosphorus entering the bay from rivers, even though the absolute loading of phosphorus from the rivers is greater than the absolute loading from point sources along the bay. This effect arises from the much greater displacement of water from the bay which accompanies the high flow volume of the rivers. The point sources contribute low flow volumes (containing high phosphorus concentrations) and consequently displace much less water from the bay.

The analyses of Johnson and Owen (1971) provide another reason for distinguishing between the effects on Lake Erie of point sources located directly on the lake shores and point sources located inland from the lake. These latter point sources empty into rivers and the phosphorus is delivered to the lake during times of high flow and low concentration.

Although the removal of phosphorus at inland point sources could result in improvements of instream water quality, such improvements would have to be associated with a reduction of nuisance algal growths in the streams. Such growths are very infrequent and are associated with low flows during which the rivers become lakelike. Baker and Kramer (1971) have postulated that flow augmentation from the upground reservoirs proposed within the Northwest Ohio Water Development Plan (Ohio Department of Natural Resources 1967) may be more effective in preventing such algal growths than phosphorus removal.

It may be necessary to reduce phosphorus loading from diffuse sources into Lake Erie in order to achieve the desired phosphorus concentrations in Lake Erie. Although the reduction of diffuse phosphorus loading may be viewed as a farm problem, in a larger sense it is probably a land use problem. Substantial reductions in diffuse phosphorus loading will require not only appropriate land use planning, but also wide spread implementation. Whereas

the installation of phosphorus removal at a domestic sewage treatment plant results in a quantifiable reduction in phosphorus output of the plant, quantification of results in the reduction of phosphorus loading from diffuse sources is much more difficult. What is needed is a eutrophication index for evaluating the impact of the land use policies of an area on its water resources. A diffuse source loading coefficient used for phosphorus and/or sediments could provide such an index. Stream monitoring programs could then be used to set priorities for land use planning and implementation, as well as to follow progress. Methods for correcting the coefficients for variations in runoff would have to be developed.

To the extent that resources currently being devoted to phosphorus removal at domestic sewage treatment plants in the inland portions of agricultural river basins could significantly augment the study and control of phosphorus loading from diffuse sources, a redirection of these resources could result in a greater benefit for Lake Erie. The total benefits from improved land use in the Lake Erie Basin will be much broader than merely a reduction of phosphorus loading into Lake Erie.

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